

Synthesis of novel 3-substitued coumarin carboxamides with biological interest and their spectral studies

Asish R. Das*, Arunima Medda, Raghunath Singha**, Anuva Samanta and Nikhil Guchhait

Department of Chemistry, University Colleges of Science, Calcutta University,
92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : ardas66@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : The 3-substitued coumarin carboxamides are prepared by a highly efficient one-pot procedure. The coupling reaction of coumarin carboxylic acids and its acid chlorides with different amines afforded amide derivatives of coumarin in moderate to high yields by using either HOBT/EDCI or NaHCO₃. In addition, we have studied photophysical pro-perties by steady state absorption and emission spectroscopy.

Keywords : Synthesis, characterization, electronic spectroscopy.

Introduction

Synthetic significance of coumarin derivatives logically comes from the established bioactivities associated with coumarins¹. Many derivatives, commonly containing hydroxy substituents, are naturally-occurring compounds and a number of these products show marked physiological effects, for example active hypotoxicity, carcinogenicity, anticoagulant action and antibiotic activity². Similarly, geiparvin – a coumarin derivative possesses an efficient anti-tumor activity³. Compounds based on the coumarin ring system give rise to one of the most extensively investigated and commercially significant groups of organic fluorescent materials⁴. In addition,

in biological and medical research, providing a useful tool in the search for new biologically active compounds and in the development of new diagnostic methods^{1,5}. It is expected that coumarin-carboxamide products could be a new class of compounds of interest in biology and pharmacology. Recently some 3-carboxamide-coumarin derivatives (compound 6h and compound 3a) offered potent and selective-FXIIa inhibitory properties⁶.

Results and discussion

Our interest is to synthesize and then to investigate the biological activities of 3-carboxamide coumarin derivatives. Our synthetic pathways are depicted below :

where, R = phenylethyl-, 2-pyridylmethyl-, 2-thiophenmethyl-, cyclohexylmethyl-

Scheme 1

tion, analytical techniques involving the use of fluorescent coumarin derivatives are of considerable importance

In the present work, new coumarin-3-carboxamides (3) (Scheme 1) were prepared by the reaction between

**Present address : Chemgen Pharma International Pvt. Limited, Kolkata, India.

where, R = 2-methoxybenzyl-, 4-chlorobenzyl-, 3,5-difluorobenzyl-, 4-chlorophenyl-, 4-methoxyphenyl-, 2-thiazolayl-, fenchyl-, phenyl-, β -naphthyl-

Scheme 2

coumarin-3-carboxylic acid (1) with different amines (2) at room temperature by using the coupling reagent HOBt/EDCI. Coumarin-3-carboxylic acid (1) and acid chloride (4) were prepared by the reported procedure⁷. Some of the new coumarin-3-carboxamides (6) (Scheme 2) were also prepared by the reaction between coumarin-3-carboxylic acid chloride (4) with different amines (5) at room temperature by using NaHCO₃. The process was also

found to be simple and advantageous.

Physical data of the new compounds (3, Scheme 1 and 6, Scheme 2) are listed in Table 1. The structures of all of them have been unambiguously characterized on the basis of their ¹H NMR and mass spectral data.

The above mentioned procedures provide a simple and a facile entry in to a variety of coumarin carboxamides

Table 1. Compounds 3 and 6 (Schemes 1 and 2)

Substrate	Amines (RNH ₂)	Time (h)	Product	Yield (%)
1	R = Phenylethyl (2a)	12	2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-(phenylethyl)carboxamide (3a)	68
	2-Pyridylmethyl (2b)	12	2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-(2-pyridylmethyl)carboxamide (3b)	72
	2-Thiophenmethyl (2c)	12	2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-(2-thiophenmethyl)carboxamide (3c)	65
	Cyclohexylmethyl (2d)	12	2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-(cyclohexylmethyl)carboxamide (3d)	69
	2-Methoxybenzyl (5a)	10	2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-(2-methoxybenzyl)carboxamide (6a)	58
	4-Chlorobenzyl (5b)	10	2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-(4-chlorobenzyl)carboxamide (6b)	65
	3,5-Difluorobenzyl (5c)	10	2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-(3,5-difluorobenzyl)carboxamide (6c)	62
	4-Chlorophenyl (5d)	10	2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-(4-chlorophenyl)carboxamide (6d)	66
	4-Methoxyphenyl (5e)	10	2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)carboxamide (6e)	69
	2-Thiazolayl (5f)	10	2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-(2-thiazolayl)carboxamide (6f)	63
	Fenchyl (5g)	10	2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-(fenchyl)carboxamide (6g)	58
	Phenyl (5h)	10	2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-(phenyl)carboxamide (6h) ^a	69
	β -Naphthyl (5i)	10	2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-(β -naphthyl)carboxamide (6i) ^a	66

^aPrepared by slightly modified procedure (reported in Experimental section).

conveniently substituted in position 3. These methods can easily be adopted to more elaborated systems, and further studies are in progress.

Photophysical properties :

(A) Absorption spectra :

The spectral properties of some of the synthesized coumarin derivatives in choice were monitored in cyclohexane, acetonitrile and methanol solvent at room temperature and the concentration were maintained within the range 10^{-5} – 10^{-6} M. The absorption spectra of different derivatives are shown in Fig. 1 and presented in Table 2. The absorption spectra (Hitachi UV-Vis, Model U-3501) of coumarin derivatives exhibited two maxima, one in the lower wavelength range (~ 280 nm) and another in the higher wavelength range (~ 330 nm) due to

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of different coumarin derivatives.

Fig. 2. Emission spectra of coumarin derivatives ($\lambda_{ext} = 330$ nm).

the transition from S_0 state to S_2 and S_1 state respectively. High absorbance values indicate that these transitions arise from $\pi\pi^*$ transition of the main aromatic unit. Structural calculations at density functional theory level

Fig. 3. Calculated molecular orbitals of 6f at DFT level.

using B3LYP functional and 6-31G** basis set have been performed for one of the coumarin derivative (6f). The calculated molecular orbitals (Fig. 3) show that the $\pi\pi^*$ transitions are located at the big ring. At the small ring side $\pi\pi^*$ transition are of higher in energy.

(B) Emission spectra :

During the excitation of each molecule at their corresponding absorption band each coumarin derivatives shows single emission band (Perkin-Elmer : Model LS-50B fluorimeter) in the wavelength range 405–420 nm which was assigned to emission from their locally excited state. Emission spectra are shown in Fig. 2 and spectral data are presented in Table 2. The emissive behaviour of these compounds were similar in polar protic and aprotic sol-

Table 2. Spectroscopic properties of some of the coumarin derivatives obtained from steady state absorption and emission spectral data

Name of the compounds	λ_{abs} (nm)	λ_{em} (nm)	ϵ ($\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ lit cm}^{-1}$)	Quantum yield (ϕ_f) $\times 10^3$
Cou-2-thiazolayl	300, 340	405	44275	1.587
Cou-2-methoxybenzyl	292, 329	410	14811	0.404
Cou-4-methoxyphenyl	280, 340	410	107125	0.4486
Cou-phenylethyl	295, 328	410	15501	1.620
Cou-2-thiophenmethyl	295, 330	410	7209	0.912
Cou-naphth	272, 335	420	110492	0.393
Cou-phenyl	302, 333	415	21461	0.086

vent, but in non-polar solvent, they were practically non-fluorescent in nature. Usually coumarin derivatives are highly fluorescent in nature and are used as laser dyes due to high fluorescence quantum yield. We have measured fluorescence quantum yield of these coumarin derivatives by secondary method using β -naphthol as reference ($\phi_{\text{ref}} = 0.23$ in methyl cyclohexane) whereas the molar extinction coefficient values were calculated using the equation,

$$[\text{O.D}] = \epsilon \cdot c \cdot l$$

where [O.D], ϵ , c , l are optical density, molar extinction coefficient, concentration of the solution in mol/lit and optical path length respectively. As shown in Table 2, the fluorescence quantum yield of these studied coumarin systems are not so high as laser dyes. Presence of flexible sites in the molecules may be used as energy dissipation paths and hence fluorescence quantum yield is very low. This has been verified by measurement of emission spectra in the micellar medium. It is found that fluorescence intensity enhances with addition of the fluorophore solution in 5 mM sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) solution due to reduction in the non-radiative deactivation rate within the hydrophobic interior of micelles. Micelles encapsulate the fluorescent molecules to reduce flexible motion and hence decrease non-radiative energy dissipation channels.

Experimental

CC : silica gel (100–200 mesh). IR spectra were recorded as KBr discs with a Perkin-Elmer Fourier Transform spectrometer. ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded in 500 MHz Bruker and 300 MHz Bruker Supercon NMR respectively, and mass spectra were recorded in LC-MS-MS of Water Micro Mass instruments.

General procedure for the preparation of compound (3) :

To a stirred solution of 3-coumarin carboxylic acid (1) (2.63 mmol) in dichloromethane, HOBT (1-hydroxybenzotriazole) (2.7 mmol) and EDCI [1-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-3-ethylcarbodiimide hydrochloride] (2.9 mmol) were added at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min, after which the amine compound (3.9 mmol) in dichloromethane was added. The reaction mixture was stirred for 12 h. After checking the TLC, the reaction mixture was quenched by adding ice-cold water. The aqueous mixture was extracted with dichloromethane (3×15 mL) and the organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The solvent (dichloromethane) was removed *in vacuo*, get a solid product which was further purified by column chromatography using silica gel (100–200 mesh) (eluent ethylacetate : hexane :: 2 : 3) to get the pure compound (3).

General procedure for the preparation of compound (6) :

The 3-coumarin carboxylic acid chloride (0.95 mmol) was added to a stirred solution of amine (0.76 mmol) in acetone or dichloromethane (toluene in case of amine **5i**) and NaHCO_3 (5.9 mmol) (triethylamine and imidazole in case of amines **5h** and **5i** respectively) at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for about ten hours. It was then filtered (excluding compounds **6h** and **6i**) and the solid was washed with acetone (or dichloromethane). The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the obtained solid was diluted with water. The aqueous mixture was extracted with dichloromethane (3×15 mL) and the organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The solvent (dichloromethane) was removed *in vacuo* to get a solid product which was further purified by column chromatography using silica gel (100–200 mesh) (eluent ethylacetate : hexane :: 2 : 3) to get the pure compound (6).

Physical and spectral data of all the synthesized compounds are summarized as below :

3a : 2-Oxo-2*H*-1-benzopyran-3-(phenylethyl)carboxamide : yield 68%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3326 (N-H), 1711 (O=C=O), 1525 (O=C-N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 8.90 (1H, s, pyran), 8.86 (1H, s, NH), 7.69–7.64 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.40–7.22 (7H, m, Ar-H), 3.72 (2H, q, J 7 and 6 Hz, phenylethyl), 2.94 (2H, t, J 7.5 and 7 Hz, phenylethyl); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ_c 161.40, 154.41, 148.23, 138.78, 133.97, 129.77, 128.69, 126.53, 125.24, 118.56, 116.60, 41.33, 35.64; MS : m/z 294 (M^+).

3b : 2-Oxo-2*H*-1-benzopyran-3-(2-pyridylmethyl)carboxamide : yield 72%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3310 (N-H), 1716 (O=C=O), 1513 (O=C-N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 9.62 (1H, s, NH), 8.94 (1H, s, pyran), 8.62 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.71–7.65 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.43–7.20 (4H, m, Ar-H), 4.83 (2H, d, J 5 Hz, pyridylmethyl); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ_c 161.70, 161.21, 156.72, 154.49, 149.39, 148.40, 136.73, 134.02, 129.77, 125.21, 122.31, 121.70, 118.56, 116.63, 45.34; MS : m/z 281 (M^+).

3c : 2-Oxo-2*H*-1-benzopyran-3-(2-thiophenmethyl)carboxamide : yield 65%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3332 (N-H), 1709 (O=C=O), 1518 (O=C-N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 9.19 (1H, s, NH), 8.95 (1H, s, pyran), 7.71–7.65 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.41–7.37 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.23 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.05 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, Ar-H), 6.96 (1H, t, J 4.5 and 4 Hz, Ar-H), 4.83 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, thiophenmethyl); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ_c 161.33, 154.48, 148.68, 140.47, 134.15, 129.83, 126.83, 126.11, 125.26, 118.60, 118.27, 116.65, 38.57; MS : m/z 285.9 (M^+).

3d : 2-Oxo-2*H*-1-benzopyran-3-(cyclohexylmethyl)carboxamide : yield 69%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3350 (N-H), 1710 (O=C=O), 1526 (O=C-N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 8.91 (1H, s, pyran), 8.87 (1H, s, NH), 7.75–7.65 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.48–7.36 (2H, m, Ar-H), 3.32 (2H, t, J 5 Hz, cyclohexylmethyl), 1.81–1.61 (6H, m, cyclohexane), 1.27–1.19 (3H, m, cyclohexane), 1.03–1.00 (2H, m, cyclohexane); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ_c 161.50, 154.39, 148.19, 133.90, 129.75, 125.23, 118.66, 116.59, 64.14, 37.86, 30.91, 26.36, 25.83, 15.24; MS : m/z 286 (M^+).

6a : 2-Oxo-2*H*-1-benzopyran-3-(2-methoxybenzyl)carboxamide (this compound was obtained as rotamer) : yield 58%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3436 (N-H), 1716 (O=C=O), 1244 (O=C-N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 9.34, 8.91 (1H, s, pyran), 7.98 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.69–7.24 (11H, m, Ar-H), 6.95–6.89 (4H, m, Ar-H), 4.9 (2H, s, NH), 4.72–4.59 (4H, m, benzyl), 3.92, 3.83 (3H, s, OCH_3); ^{13}C NMR

(CDCl_3) δ_c 160.87, 160.44, 156.87, 153.79, 147.48, 143.85, 141.95, 133.99, 132.66, 130.18, 129.0, 128.43, 128.25, 128.13, 124.95, 124.87, 120.13, 118.82, 118.39, 116.09, 110.58, 55.30; MS : m/z 310 (M^+ , 30%).

6b : 2-Oxo-2*H*-1-benzopyran-3-(4-chlorobenzyl)carboxamide : yield 65%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3340 (N-H), 1719 (O=C=O), 1526 (O=C-N); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 9.16 (1H, s, NH), 8.87 (1H, s, pyran), 7.99 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.75 (1H, t, J 7 and 1.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.52 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.46–7.37 (5H, m, Ar-H), 4.54 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, benzyl); ^{13}C NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ_c 161.91, 160.71, 154.35, 148.02, 138.51, 134.63, 131.96, 130.71, 129.75, 128.75, 125.64, 119.53, 118.88, 116.61, 42.56; MS : m/z 314 (M^+ , 25%).

6c : 2-Oxo-2*H*-1-benzopyran-3-(3,5-difluorobenzyl)carboxamide : yield 62%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3325 (N-H), 1713 (O=C=O), 1527 (O=C-N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 9.26 (1H, s, NH), 8.95 (1H, s, pyran), 7.72–7.67 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.44–7.39 (2H, m, Ar-H), 6.88 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, Ar-H), 6.73–6.69 (1H, m, Ar-H), 4.64 (2H, d, J 6.5 Hz, benzyl); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ_c 161.87, 161.48, 154.53, 148.96, 134.34, 129.91, 125.42, 118.58, 118.07, 116.71, 110.47, 110.14, 43.01, 30.83; MS : m/z 315.9 (M^+ , 14%).

6d : 2-Oxo-2*H*-1-benzopyran-3-(4-chlorophenyl)carboxamide : yield 66%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3423 (N-H), 1700 (O=C=O), 1552 (O=C-N); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 10.74 (1H, s, NH), 8.92 (1H, s, pyran), 8.03 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.79 (3H, t, J 10 and 5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.57 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, Ar-H), 7.50–7.45 (3H, m, Ar-H); MS : m/z 300 (M^+).

6e : 2-Oxo-2*H*-1-benzopyran-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)carboxamide : yield 69%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3277 (N-H), 1705 (O=C=O), 1500 (O=C-N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 10.72 (1H, s, NH), 9.01 (1H, s, pyran), 7.74–7.65 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.46–7.41 (2H, m, Ar-H), 6.92 (2H, d, J 10 Hz, Ar-H), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH_3); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ_c 161.82, 159.01, 156.76, 154.45, 148.57, 134.18, 130.90, 129.86, 125.41, 122.10, 118.77, 116.68, 114.22, 55.47; MS : m/z 296 (M^+).

6f : 2-Oxo-2*H*-1-benzopyran-3-(2-thiazolayl)carboxamide : yield 63%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3427 (N-H), 1702 (O=C=O), 1542 (O=C-N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 12.00 (1H, s, NH), 9.03 (1H, s, pyran), 7.77–7.73 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.56 (1H, d, J 3.5 Hz, Ar-H), 7.48–7.43 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.07 (1H, d, J 3.5 Hz, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ_c 149.89, 138.40, 135.10, 130.19, 125.68,

118.44, 116.84, 114.44, 65.81, 15.23; MS : m/z 272.9 (M^+).

6g : 2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-(fenchyl)carboxamide : yield 58%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3346 (N-H), 1107 (-O-C=O), 1530 (O=C-N); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 9.02 (1H, s, NH), 8.91 (1H, s, pyran), 7.69-7.64 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.42-7.36 (2H, m, Ar-H), 3.83 (1H, q, J 1.5 and 7.5 Hz, fenchyl), 1.8-1.7 (3H, m, Ar-H), 1.52-1.48 (2H, m, fenchyl), 1.26 (2H, t, J 10 and 10.5 Hz, fenchyl), 1.17 (3H, s, fenchyl), 1.09 (3H, s, fenchyl), 0.86 (3H, s, fenchyl); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ_c 162.0, 161.74, 154.41, 148.1, 133.89, 129.77, 125.27, 118.79, 116.64, 64.54, 48.88, 48.32, 42.74, 39.76, 31.02, 27.55, 26.02, 21.49, 19.75; MS : m/z 126 (M^+).

6h : 2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-(phenyl)carboxamide : yield 69%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3273 (N-H), 1708 (-O-C=O), 1550 (O=C-N); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 10.84 (1H, s, NH), 9.03 (1H, s, pyran), 7.75-7.69 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.46-7.37 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.27 (3H, d, J 9 Hz, Ar-H), 7.17 (1H, t, J 7.5 Hz, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ_c 161.81, 159.29, 154.5, 148.93, 137.65, 134.34, 129.93, 129.05, 125.46, 124.82, 120.58, 118.7, 116.72; MS : m/z 266 (M^+ , 90%).

6i : 2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-3-(β -naphthyl)carboxamide : yield 66%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3422 (N-H), 1705 (-O-C=O), 1516 (O=C-N); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 11.03 (1H, s, NH), 9.06 (1H, s, pyran), 8.47 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.86-7.66 (6H, m, Ar-H), 7.48-7.41 (4H, m, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ_c 161.88, 159.47, 154.54, 148.92, 135.14, 134.38, 133.89, 130.98, 129.97, 128.81, 127.88, 127.58, 126.51, 125.5, 125.22, 120.42, 118.78, 118.72, 117.57, 116.75; MS : m/z 316 (M^+ , 95%).

Conclusion :

Our endeavor towards the development of a new series of compounds clearly indicates that 3-carboxamide

coumarins are very potent biologically with selective non peptidic inhibitory properties⁶. The novel findings are in progress and will be communicated shortly.

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